

ESTABLISHING DAMAGE SCENARIO OF RANDOMLY ORIENTED STRAND (ROS) THERMOSET COMPOSITES USING MULTI-INSTRUMENTATION AND MICRO-CT

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ABSTRACT

Among the factors limiting the use of composite materials are the complex shapes to be found, for example, in aircraft engines. A new and innovative composite material (HexMC[®]), unidirectional prepreg based, made of long and discontinuous strands (or “chips”) and randomly oriented, seems to match the demands. The goal of this study is to characterize the first damages that initiate the failure under tensile loading in the particular case of HexMC[®]. For this purpose, various and multi-instrumented (Digital Image Correlation (DIC), Acoustic Emission (AE), post-mortem/in-situ microscopy and tomography) tensile tests were conducted. Not only the types of damage were determined (intra and inter-strand debonding) but also the sequence in which they appear and the way they propagate. Initiation of the first damages is attributed to strands roughly oriented at 90° with respect to the loading direction. These particular strands are the ones in which appear the first intra-strand debonding transversely to the loading direction. In addition, the loading level at which occur the first damages is determined. Finally, through this study and the multi-instrumented analyses, a scenario of the first damage mechanisms was developed.

1 INTRODUCTION

In order to keep lightening the new generation of aeronautical structures, it is necessary to diversify and to expand the fields of parts made in composite materials. These materials offer the benefits of low weight and good mechanical properties. However, among the factors limiting their use are the complex shapes to be found, for example, in aircraft engines. In one hand, short fiber composites, which allow the manufacturing of complex parts, do not have sufficient mechanical properties to match design requirements because of their low fiber volume fraction. In the other hand, continuous fiber composites are not flexible enough to fit the complex mold shape. Thus, a new and innovative composite material made of discontinuous and long fibers (DLF) appears able to bridge the gap between mechanical performance (up to 60% fiber volume fraction) and a shaping approaching short fiber composite one, thanks to discontinuities. DLF composites are made of unidirectional strands (or “chips”) which are prepreg based and randomly oriented. DLF composites are also called ROS composites (Randomly Oriented Strand composites) in the literature. They offer the advantage of a reduced manufacturing, cutting and draping time cost compared to liquid composite molding (LCM) for example.

In the literature, a number of studies have been conducted to determining the main mechanical properties such as Young modulus and ultimate strength under tensile testing. ROS composites show a high level of randomness and appear to be strongly heterogeneous because of their mesostructure. In the first place, some authors experimentally explored the influence of parameters such as defects, thickness and width of either the specimens or the strands, etc., on the mechanical response at macroscopic scale [1-7]. Manufacturing process is also an important parameter as mechanical properties of composite parts are strongly linked to their processing. Thermocompression is used in the case of ROS composites and some authors studied its impact on the health, on the defect and on the mechanical response of ROS composite parts [8-13]. A few 3D numerical models were developed to simulate the elastic behavior of ROS composites under tensile loading. Most of them show good correlation with experimental data when partitioning the specimens into many random laminate composites [14]. However, from a sizing

and designing point of view, it seems essential to introduce the concept of damage mechanisms to link to the mesostructure.

A few studies focused on damage characterization. The stochastic nature of ROS composites makes the understanding of damage phenomena much harder. Heterogeneity and local spots of strain concentration are typical of ROS composites [1-3, 9] but no link was established neither between the stress level of the first damages and the ultimate strength nor between the location of the first damages and the final fracture location [15]. In addition and despite the use of Digital Image Correlation (DIC), allowing the potential locations of failure to be detected, it was impossible to predict which strain spots would actually lead to the failure. Some authors incriminate the strand discontinuities, corresponding to the strand borders, to be responsible for crack initiation [1-2, 7] whereas others incriminate defects, resin pocket or strands transversely oriented [15-17]. Concerning the course of events leading to the failure, some authors consider a simultaneous appearance of the different types of damage [4] while others consider sequential progress of the damage scenario [16-18].

Nevertheless, opinions are divided about the cracking initiation. This is mainly due to the large diversity of the ROS composites that differ from one study to the other in terms of components (fibers, matrix) and processing. In addition, most of the observation belong to surface observation types (DIC, microscopy). The acoustic emission technique (AE) could be very useful for following damage mechanisms during loading phases. AE and tomography, which are volume techniques, are both of considerable interest especially for ROS composites, given their stochastic orientation and layout.

The goal of this study is to characterize damages under tensile loading, in the particular case of HexMC[®], a ROS composite manufactured by Hexcel[™]. Various and multi-instrumented (DIC, AE, microscopy, tomography) tensile tests were conducted in order to determine, on the one hand, the existing types of damage and, on the other hand, the sequence in which they appeared and the way they propagated. The objective is to develop a scenario of the damage mechanisms involved and to determine the predominant factors governing the cracking initiation.

First, HexMC[®] and the specimen preparation will be presented. Then, the experimental setup and the general methodology followed will be described. Finally, the last sections will deal with results from microscopy, DIC, AE and tomography.

2 MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This study focuses on a particular ROS composite, HexMC[®].

2.1 Material

HexMC[®] is a sheet made of unidirectional carbon (AS4[®]) / epoxy (8552[®]) prepreg strands, randomly oriented and distributed. Strands are 50mm long, 8mm wide and 0.13mm thick and cut from a unidirectional prepreg sheet. Plies are cut from this HexMC[®] sheet and then laid up just like a standard laminated composite. The layup is finally cured and polymerized by thermocompression. The fiber volume fraction reaches 57% but varies locally since strands are spatially stochastic. In this study, HexMC[®] panels of 5.25mm thick were manufactured.

2.2 Specimens

Dog bone specimens (Fig. 1) were machined in the 5.25mm HexMC[®] panels with a cutting machine as Charlyrobot[™]. The dog bone shape was preferred to straight shape to facilitate the rupture in the Area Of Interest (AOI). Glass tabs are bonded to the specimen extremities with Aradlite2015[®] adhesive to avoid any stress concentration close to the jaws of the tensile testing machine. The specimen sides are manually (because of dog bone shape, the polishing machine is useless) polished until FEPA #4000. Polishing is made in order to realize a microscopic scan of the mesostructure at the initial uncharged state but also during a loading phase or post-mortem. Both sides of every specimens are polished because phenomena could be very different on the two sides because of the mesostructure of HexMC[®]. Speckling is applied to each face of the AOI (Fig. 1). These two faces were photographed before the application of speckling. These images allowed the DIC fields to be linked to the mesostructure.

Figure 1: Tensile test specimen geometry.

2.3 Experimental setup

Tensile tests driven with a displacement rate of 1mm/min are realized on an electro-mechanical testing machine of 100kN capacity. The specimens are instrumented with two micro-80 AE sensors (100 kHz – 1MHz), 85mm far from each other. These AE sensors allow the acoustic hits, generated by damages, to be localized in the AOI (Fig. 2). A coupling gel is applied between AE sensors and the specimen to improve the acquisition of the hits. The acoustic wave velocity is evaluated with a pencil lead breaking test on the surface of the specimen. The time parameters (μs) of acquisition, Peak Definition Time (PDT), Hit Definition Time (HDT) and Hit Lockout Time (HLT) are respectively (30, 150, and 300) and the acquisition threshold is set at 40dB. The softwares AEwin[®] and Noesis[®] developed by Mistras[™] are respectively used for the acquisition and the post-processing of AE data. In addition, two Stereo-correlated camera systems are set up on each face of the AOI. From DIC analyses, these two Stereo-correlated systems will allow the displacements and the strain fields to be measured at the surface of the AOI. The acquisition and post-processing of the DIC data are made respectively with VIC-Snap[®] and VIC3D[®] software developed by Correlated Solution[™]. The sampling rate is one image per second and the exposure time is 9ms. The camera resolution is 2048x2048 pixels and the AOI is about 1600 pixels high and 750 pixels wide. The use of a DIC system on each face of the AOI is motivated by the stochastic nature of the HexMC[®] mesostructure that can lead to different strain fields on each face.

Figure 2 : Experimental setup.

3 METHODOLOGY

Three kinds of testing were performed. First, monotonous tensile tests were done to obtain the macroscopic mechanical behavior of HexMC[®]. In addition, the Young modulus and the ultimate strength were measured and the stress level of the first AE hit appearances was determined to manage the following tests.

Second, incremental tensile loading tests were executed (every 5kN from first damages detected with the previous tests). These tests are useful when using the “gap to the elastic load to strain ratio”

method [18]. This method, based on strain fields calculated by DIC, provide information about a potential and local loss of stiffness in the material because of damages that occurred during the loading phases. In facts, for each loading phases, a ratio representative of the compliance of the material ($\epsilon_{11,local} / \sigma_{11,nominal}$) is calculated in every DIC data points of the AOI. $\epsilon_{11,local}$ is the local strain in the loading direction determined by DIC and $\sigma_{11,nominal}$ is the nominal stress in the loading direction. This method provides thereby a representative map of the compliance of the material. When a damage occurs, it locally causes a loss of stiffness. Therefore, this method allows the detection of the first sites of damages by comparing the compliance ratio of the different loading phases. The comparison can be performed either systematically with the initial loading phase or incrementally. The technique is directly dependent on the DIC parameters and a sensibility survey, not presented in this article, was conducted in order to determine the best compromise between noise and spatial resolution. Using VIC3D[®], the selected parameter (subset, step, filter size) are, in pixels, respectively (11, 1, 15).

This second type of tests is also done for tomographic analyses. Following every tensile loading phases, a unique specimen is placed into the tomographic device. Tomography is performed with a 37 μ m voxel size. This protocol allows the detection of damages inside the specimen, which are linked to the stress level.

Third, incremental loading plateau tests were performed. When the maximum of charge of a loading phase is reached, a microscopic scan of both specimen sides is realized in situ with a video-microscope. These scans allowed the types of damage to be determined and the follow-up of their evolution and their propagation according to the stress state of the specimen. Finally, a chronological occurrence of damages is deduced.

4 RESULTS

The HexMC[®] mechanical behavior under tensile loading is quasi-elastic and the failure is fragile. No non-linearity caused by damages are detected with the stress/strain tensile curve. The linear regression computed fit quasi-perfectly with the experimental curve (Fig. 3). The young modulus is measured from the slope of the stress/strain graph between 0.1% and 0.3% strain.

Figure 3 : Quasi-elastic and fragile behavior of HexMC[®] under tensile loading.

4.1 Microscopic observations

Post-Mortem microscopic scans were executed. The fiber orientations were identified and divided into three classes. Relatively to the loading direction, strands oriented between 60° and 90°, between 30° and 60° and between 0° and 30° are respectively assigned to class A, B and C. According

to these microscopic observations, the main damages identified were intra-strand and inter-strand debonding (Fig. 4). Only a few fiber failures were listed.

Figure 4 : Observations of Post-Mortem damages.

According to the in-situ microscopic scans realized during the loading plateau, intra-strand debonding seem to be the first kind of damage to occur and take place in strands transversely oriented (class A) relatively to the loading direction. The first intra-strand debonding observed, occurred around a stress level of 200-225MPa. The next loading plateau provided information about the expansion of the initial cracks and allowed the detection of new sites of damages. Two ways of damage expansion were observed. First, multi-cracking of a unique transversely oriented strand (Fig. 5a), and second, propagation of the intra-strand debonding in the neighboring strands. In the second case, if the neighboring strand is oriented in parallel to the initial strand, the cracks spread in a quasi-straight line (Fig. 4) and remains intra-strand debonding, whereas if the neighboring strand is strongly disoriented compared to the initial strand, the intra-strand debonding spreads into an inter-strand debonding (Fig. 5b). It seems that inter-strand debonding only occurred as the propagation of an intra-strand debonding. Inter-strand debonding does not initiate by itself. However, damages are not confined to a unique site. This means that if the crack initiation is caused by intra-strand debonding in strongly disoriented strands with respect to the loading direction, both intra and inter-strand debonding appear in parallel in other sites of the specimen as soon as the load exceeds the loading level at which occur the first damages.

Figure 5 : Damage expansion, (a) intra-strand multi-cracking, (b) inter-strand debonding.

4.2 DIC analyses and “gap to the elastic load to strain ratio”

Potential sites of damages were determined through DIC and the use of the “gap to the elastic load to strain ratio” technique. Strain spots are very heterogeneous, focused and their straight outlines are typical (Fig. 6a). When superimposing the strain fields and the mesostructure, it is obvious that strain spots are concentrated at strand edges (Fig. 6b). Nevertheless, all strain spots do not necessarily lead to cracks. The “gap to the elastic load to strain ratio” technique, using an incremental comparison, indicated that only a few strain spots turned into cracks. First damage detectable with the “gap to the elastic load to strain ratio” technique, belonged to a transversely oriented strand edge and occurred between 200 and 225MPa (Fig. 6c).

Figure 6 : From DIC to the mesostructure, (a) compliance ratio mapping during the 45kN loading phase, (b) surface mesostructure, (c) “gap to the elastic load to strain ratio” incremental technique between 40 and 45kN loading phases.

A link was established between the mesostructure and the strain fields. The transversely oriented strands seems to be responsible for damage initiation around 200MPa. However, limitations of both DIC and microscopy are highlighted because of the surface aspect of these techniques. They do not take into account the phenomenons happening through the thickness.

4.3 Acoustic Emission

The use of AE is motivated by the volume aspect of this technique, which takes into account what happens through the thickness. First, EA technique allowed the repeatability with which the several specimens are damaged to be examined. By comparing the energetic signature of every specimens, it was shown that despite of the stochastic structure of the HexMC[®], the first damages occurred always from almost the same loading level – around 200MPa (Fig. 7). For these results, only the localized acoustic hits were taken into account.

Figure 7 : Comparison of energetic signature under tensile loading.

Second, AE allowed the acoustic waveforms to be clustered. The main idea for clustering is to create groups of similar acoustic waveforms. In this study, the “k-means” method was used. This unsupervised method only requires an initial set of acoustic parameters and the final number of clusters wanted. The first step consisted of determining the relevant set of acoustic parameters that would allow an accurate segregation of AE waveforms. A correlation analysis through dendrogram was performed and the final acoustic parameters were selected to be at least 0.1 non-correlated (Tab. 1).

Temporal parameters	Risetime	Absolute Energy	Duration	Amplitude
Frequency parameters	Average frequency	-	-	-

Tab. 1 : Final choice of the AE parameters.

Once the acoustic parameters are determined, the choice of the number of clusters must be done. Davies&Bouldin (D&B) is an analytical criterion that provides an indication of the optimal number of clusters to be chosen. In this study, D&B criterion preconizes three clusters. However, D&B criterion is “only” a mathematical indicator and it remains to the operator to choose the number of clusters according to his knowledge of the material (thanks to observations for example). In the present study, the number of potential cluster was set to two according to the 4.1 and 4.2 sections. In the facts and following a sensitive survey, a number of four clusters was chosen because it highlights the best the phenomenons observed (Fig. 8).

Figure 8 : Example of AE hits clustering – 4 clusters

The first cluster made of a large number of hits is not very energetic and occurred from the beginning of the tensile test. This cluster is not representative of any damage and is attributed to minor non-damaging phenomena. The fourth cluster contains a unique and very energetic hit, which occurred at the very end of the tensile test. This cluster is attributed to the catastrophic failure. The two clusters remaining, according to their occurrence, their energy, their number of hits and their chronology, seems to be representatives of the damaging behavior. The second cluster really exhibits its development around 190MPa and the third cluster around 230 MPa. The second cluster is less energetic and occurred before the third cluster, and have a larger number of hits than the third one. For each cluster, the temporal and frequency parameter centers are calculated. Given a cluster, centers can be seen as the centroids or the means of each temporal and frequency parameters. These centers will help when labelling. Due to the extreme nature of the hit in the fourth cluster, this cluster will not appear in the next diagrams because of the phenomenon of cluster-flattening when normalizing. The attribution of a cluster to a kind of damage was done with respect to the acoustic characteristics of matrix cracking, debonding, delamination and fiber breakage found in the literature [20, 21].

The cluster centers of the specimens, namely (a, b, c, d), show a good repeatability (Fig. 9). The first cluster shows insignificant values for every temporal acoustic parameters and a high average frequency (afreq). According to previous ascertainments, it confirms that the first cluster can be attributed to minor phenomena not involved in the damage mechanisms. The second cluster is attributed to intra-strand debonding. Compared to third cluster hits, hits belonging to the second cluster have a lower amplitude (ampl), are less energetic (ener), are shorter (cnts, dura) and have a lower Risetime (rise, pcnt). Thus, the third cluster is attributed to inter-strand debonding.

Therefore, a damage scenario was determined through the AE analysis. The damage initiation is caused by intra-strand debonding. Then, the development of damage is due to the expansion of intra-strand debonding into inter-strand debonding in parallel of new intra-strand debonding sites.

Figure 9 : Acoustic parameter centroids diagram.

4.4 Tomography

As a 3D technique, tomographic investigations were conducted in order to corroborate the results from the previous instrumentations. A micro-CT analysis was performed on a single specimen subjected to an incremental loading plan. This tensile test allowed the detection of the type, the loading level and the location of the first damages (Fig. 10). On Figure 10, both healthy (left) and damaged (right) state of a single specimen can be seen with a focus on the damaged area. Cracks, transversely oriented with respect to the loading direction appeared to be the first damage and occurred during the 40kN – 200MPa loading phase. Unfortunately, the density of the composite components are too close from each other, and according to the area analyzed, it was impossible to get a sufficient spatial resolution to visualize the strand orientations. Nevertheless, an analogy with the microscopic observation can be done and this transverse crack can be attributed to intra-strand debonding.

Figure 10 : First damage observed from specimen's edge tomographic point of view.

To visualize the orientation of the strand in which the first damage occurred, it was necessary to change the point of view (Fig. 11). It can be seen that the first damage belongs to a strand that is roughly transversely oriented with respect to the loading direction. Unfortunately, it was impossible to visualize cracks parallel to the loading direction neither the chronological damage sequence. Because of the resin pocket located at strand ends, the inter-strand debonding are difficult to observe by tomography. However, most of the results from microscopy observations are corroborated by the volume technique of tomography.

Figure 11 : First damage observed from specimen's front tomographic point of view.

5 CONCLUSION

The combined analyses of the multi-instrumented test results allowed the determination of a damage scenario of HexMC[®] under tensile loading (Fig. 12Figure 12). Through DIC and microscopy, transversely oriented strands, with respect to the loading direction, were identified as propitious spots leading to the first damages. Through microscopy and AE, these first damages are identified as intra-strand debonding. The expansion of the first damage mechanism is characterized by the parallel development of intra and inter strand debonding. In the case of intra-strand debonding expansion, a single strand can be segmented by many intra-strand debonding (multi-cracking) or can just occur in another weak spot combining important strain and transversely oriented strand. Intra-strand debonding can also be observed as the growth of the initial crack in an adjacent strand. This happens when adjacent strands are oriented in a similar direction compared to the initial cracked strand. Thus, a quasi-straight crack, crossing several strands oriented in almost the same direction, can be observed. In the case of inter-strand debonding, it is always the result of the expansion of an intra-strand debonding. Inter-strand debonding occurs when the adjacent strands are oriented in a transverse direction compared to the initial cracked strand. Relevant results on debonding and cracking network were expected from tomography. Unfortunately, the nature of the HexMC[®] and the insufficient resolution did not allow the observation of the microstructure and thus, did not allowed the expansion of cracks within the different loading phases to be followed. Nevertheless, the few information got corroborate the microscopic observations. The catastrophic failure is fragile and includes pull-outs and a few fiber breakages. The loading level at which the first damage occurred was determined around 200MPa. From a certain point a view, the first damages behave, in the case of HexMC[®], in a similar way as they do in standard laminated and continuous composites. If the discontinuities do not seem to be responsible for the first damage appearance, it is a safe bet that they are involved in the considerable drop of the ultimate strength. Mechanisms such as the junction of previously damaged sites could explain the precipitous failure as there are no continuous fibers to carry the stress.

Following this study, a numerical model will be developed to allow a better understanding of the damage mechanism. The objective is to have a model allowing the prediction of the identified damages and their variability.

Figure 12 : Diagram of the scenario of damage mechanisms in HexMC[®] under tensile loading.

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